

J_1 and J_1 - J_2 models for the two-dimensional layered V_2VI_3 DMSs.

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Cluster tables for the first nearest-neighbor model (J_1) and the first- and second-nearest-neighbor model (J_1 - J_2) in diluted magnetic semiconductors, based on the two-dimensional layered V_2VI_3 family, have been computed for clusters up to the quintets.

We present the cluster tables for the first nearest-neighbor model (J_1) and the first and second nearest neighbor model (J_1 - J_2) in the diluted magnetic semiconductors, based on the two-dimensional layered V_2VI_3 family, such as $(Bi, Sb)_2(Te, S, Se)_3$. We assume that the magnetic ions (M) substitute for the V elements in the cationic sub lattice resulting in the composition $M_{2x}V_{2(1-x)}VI_3$. The cluster tables include clusters with one atom (single), two atoms (pair), three atoms (triplet), four atoms (quartet), and five atoms (quintet). The tables provide the configurations of the exchange bonds between the magnetic ions within each cluster and the parameters needed to calculate cluster probabilities.

The probability that a magnetic ion belongs to a cluster type with m magnetic ions is given by:

$$p(x) = \sum_k n_k x^{m-1} (1-x)^{v_k} \quad (1)$$

Here, n_k is the number of identical possible clusters with the configuration k , and x is the probability of a cation lattice site being occupied by a magnetic dopant. The term x^{m-1} represents the probability of the $m-1$ sites in the cluster being occupied, while the term $(1-x)^{v_k}$ represents the probability of the v_k vacant cation sites within the considered range of exchange interaction around the m atoms of the cluster being unoccupied. The sum is over all different configuration sets k that belong to that cluster type. The expression is based on the random distribution of the magnetic ions.

Figure 1 shows the hexagonal crystal structure of V_2VI_3 . The structure consists of quintuple layers, arranged in a sequence of five layers: VI-V-VI-V-VI. Two adjacent quintuple layers are weakly bonded by van der Waals forces. The right side of the figure displays both the nearest and second-nearest neighbors. The central cation (in color) is surrounded by six nearest neighbors within the same layer (plane A) and three second-nearest neighbors in the adjacent upper cation layer (plane B).

In the J_1 model, we have to considerate one hexagonal monolayer only. Table I and Figure 2 summarize the main results for the J_1 model. The clusters are singles, pairs, two types of triplets (labeled 1 for open and 2 for closed triplets), four types of quartets, and eight types of quintets.

Figure 1. Hexagonal crystal structure of V_2VI_3 . The large spheres represent the cations while the smaller spheres represent the anions.

Figure 2. Triplet (T.i), Quartet (Q.i), and quintet (V.i) types in the J_1 model. The lines represent the exchange bonds between magnetic ions.

Cluster	Type No.	(n_k, v_k)
Singles	1	(1,6)
Pairs	1	(6,8)
Triplets	1	(6,9)
Quartets	2	(27,10)
	1	(108,12)
	2	(8,12)
	3	(48,11)
Quintets	4	(12,10)
	1	(30,13),(375,14)
	2	(90,14)
	3	(180,13)
	4	(120,13)
	5	(15,12)
	6	(30,12)
	7	(60,12)
8	(30,11)	

Table I. Parameters n_k and v_k of the probability that a spin belongs to singles, pairs, triplets, quartets and quintet in the J_1 model for $M_{2x}V_{2(1-x)}VI_3$. The second column indicates the cluster types. The triplet, quartet and quintet types are described in the Figure 2.

Cluster size	Type No.	(n_k, v_k)
Singles	1	(1,9)
Pairs	1	(6,13)
	2	(3,12)
Triplets	1	(3,15), (3,16)
	2	(27,17)
	3	(9,14)
	4	(18,15),(18,16)
Quartets	1	(108,21)
	2	(8,21)
	3	(24,19),(24,20)
	4	(12,18)
	5	(12,16)
	6	(36,18)
	7	(4,15)
	8	(24,17),(48,18)
	9	(12,18),(24,19)
	10	(72,19),(72,20)
	11	(24,16)
	12	(24,17)
	13	(6,16)
	14	(24,18),(12,19)
	15	(12,18),(48,19),(24,20)

Table II. Parameters n_k and v_k of the probability that a spin belongs to singles, pairs, triplets and quartets in the $J_1 - J_2$ model for $M_{2x}V_{2(1-x)}VI_3$. The second column indicates the cluster types for each cluster size. For quintets, the parameters are given in the cluster tables.

In the J_1 - J_2 model, the two cation layers within each quintuple layers are considered. Table II summarizes the

results for this model. Pair 2 consists of two magnetic ions coupled by the J_2 exchange interaction. Triplets 1 and 2 are identical to those in the J_1 model. Triplet type 3 consists of mixed closed triplets, formed by two J_2 interactions and one J_1 interaction, while type 4 includes

Figure 3. Representation of the hexagonal structure in the 3D array used in the cluster tables. The k -page of the 3D array is along the \mathbf{c} -axis.

open mixed triplets with one J_2 and one J_1 . The quartet types 1 through 4 are the same as in Figure 2. The other types of quartets, from type 4 to type 15, are described using the exchange bond configurations determined by the sequence of S_1S_2 , S_1S_3 , S_1S_4 , S_2S_3 , S_2S_4 and S_3S_4 , where S_iS_j is the exchange interaction (0, 1 or 2) between the magnetic ions i and j . One configuration for quartet type 5 is (2,0,2,1,1,1); for type 6, it is (2,0,0,1,1,1); for type 7, (1,1,2,1,2,2); for type 8, (1,0,2,1,2,0); for type 9, (2,0,0,1,1,0); for type 10, (1,0,0,1,0,2); for type 11, (1,2,2,2,0,1); for type 12, (2,0,1,1,2,0); for type 13, (1,0,2,2,0,1); for type 14, (2,0,0,1,0,2); and for type 15, (1,0,0,2,0,1). For the quintets, there are 48 types in total. Quintet types 1 to 8 are the same as in the J_1 model, while the remaining 40 types are mixed clusters involving both J_2 and J_1 exchange interactions.

The cluster tables were calculated using a computer program in which the hexagonal structure is distorted to fit within a simple cubic lattice, represented by 3D arrays with i -rows, j -columns, and k -pages, as shown in Figure 3. The cluster tables are provided for magnetic ions in monolayer type A, as shown in Figure 1. For cations in plane B, the cluster tables can be obtained by applying simple point symmetry to the locations of the $m-1$ and v_k sites in the given cluster tables.

The cluster tables are provided as digital .txt files attached to this document. A README file with descriptions of the columns for each cluster size is also included.